

Norway | One Health Surveillance | Swine influenza

Background

Swine influenza was first introduced to Norwegian pig holdings during the 2009 pandemic, and only H1N1pdm09 has been detected since.

Objectives

- To enhance the virological surveillance in swine in Norway.
- Investigate whether H1N1pdm09 is established in the Norwegian swine population and thereby might be a source for transmission back to humans.
- Assess the vaccine coverage in swine workers and veterinarians working with live swine.

Outcomes & Impact

- Improved diagnostic methods at the Veterinary Institute, featuring enhanced deployment of real-time RT-PCR and optimized preparation of samples prior to RNA extraction.
- Research on the circulation of H1N1pdm09 in swine and humans (including potential human-to-swine spillovers) and results from vaccination survey will be published in peer-reviewed journals.
- Strengthened One Health collaboration (veterinary/public health).

Lessons learned

- Replacing serosurveillance with virological surveillance is not feasible due to challenging to detect the virus in samples from pigs (short shedding period and often asymptomatic pigs), particularly in situations of low prevalence.
- Need to improve virological surveillance, and whole genome sequencing of all influenza A viruses and share sequences.
- The most critical step in this pilot has been to get appropriate samples from swine with unsuspecting or subclinical influenza A

Core messages

- Collecting oral fluid samples using chewing rope reduces costs for virological surveillance of H1N1pdm09 in swine. Udder wipes may be an appropriate method to indirectly sample suckling pigs.
- Serological surveillance should be active, not only passive based on swine with clinical signs, but indications for sampling needs to be optimized.
- Challenging to track the evolution of H1N1pdm09 in swine and to compare it with the strains circulating in humans.